

ABOUT MASTER THE CRYPTO

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Keywords:

1. Background

Aziz Bin Zainuddin is a Blockchain expert with a passion for evangelizing the revolutionary technology. He is the Founder and Chief Crypto Officer of Master The Crypto, a knowledge hub & resource center that focuses on cryptocurrency investing and all things Blockchain. In addition to writing and speaking about Blockchain & Cryptocurrency, Aziz runs C.M. Fund, a Crypto Hedge Fund based in Singapore which invests in cryptos with solid fundamentals and game-changing technology.

Prior to Master the Crypto, Aziz worked in several financial technology startups that focused on Blockchain Technology and Artificial Intelligence. He was a former Investment Analyst at CG Capital Markets where he explored blockchain technologies and their application towards fintech solutions centered around the staffing industry.

Aziz is also a featured contributor for Forbes Middle East and Futurism, which is a media portal featuring the latest scientific breakthroughs and technological innovations. He regularly contributes about cryptocurrency and blockchain technology applications across a variety of industry sectors. Lastly, Aziz holds a first-class degree in Islamic Finance at the International Islamic University of Malaysia.

2. ABOUT MASTER THE CRYPTO

Master The Crypto is a knowledge hub and a resource center for everything Cryptocurrencies and Blockchain. With the technical complexities of the Cryptocurrency industry a major hurdle to the masses, MTC aims to bridge the gap by featuring articles that are broken down and easy-to-understand for many. From comprehensive guides in Crypto investing to a general overview of key technical concepts, MTC provides a wide range of content for those interested in familiarizing themselves with Cryptos.

MTC also offers supplementary learning tools to better educate our readers, through offering a free fundamental analysis checklist in the form of an eBook. A free 3-part video series has also been launched, covering the basics of Crypto investing that includes an overview of Blockchain technology, the importance of fundamental investment analysis of different Coins, as well as an introduction to technical analysis - or the study of price charts and movements - specifically geared towards the Crypto market.

February 3, 2018

With that, MTC intends to create a culture of Crypto due diligence and analytics, so as to further enhance the knowledge base of readers. We believe that knowledge is the weapon one needs to protect themselves in a highly complex and technical field.

February 3, 2018